

DISPLAY OF JOY'S MULTIDIMENSIONALITY IN ENGLISH PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS-MOTIVES

Kutlimuratova Shakhsanem Bayramovna

Student of master's degree of Uzbek state world languages university

ABSTRACT

This work is devoted to the study of the means of phraseological representation of emotive concepts in Russian and English on the example of the concept "joy". The work was carried out within the framework of cognitive phraseology, a modern direction linguistics, and is aimed at investigating the problem of the relationship between linguistic units and cognitive structures of knowledge representation in the aspect of phraseological conceptualization of selected emotions. Here you can find a number of phraseological units and their meanings.

Key words: *Linguistics, concept, phraseology, joy, happiness, cognitive, structure, world picture, emotion.*

Phraseology is a branch of linguistics that studies stable combinations in a language. Phraseology is also called a set of stable combinations in the language as a whole, in the language of a writer, in the language of a particular work of fiction, etc. Phraseology emerged relatively recently as an independent linguistic discipline. The subject and tasks, scope and methods of studying phraseology have not yet been clearly defined, and therefore have not received full coverage. Less than others, questions have been developed about the main features of phraseological units in comparison with free phrases, about the classification of phraseological units and their relationship to parts of speech, etc. Linguists have not formed a single opinion about what phraseology is, therefore, there is no unity of views on the composition of these units in the language.

The system of ideas about the world that a person develops throughout his life is gradually enriched with new knowledge that is formed into general concepts. This set consists of concepts, since a person in the process of activity and communication thinks and acts in the world of concepts that have certain characteristics and properties. The concept is the object of study of a number of sciences, such as cognitive linguistics, cultural studies, linguo-cultural studies, political science, sociology and ethnopsychology. Linguoculturology considers a set of basic concepts that collectively characterize the manifestations of culture in language and allow analyzing the relationship of language with culture in development. Currently, the concept is one of the basic concepts of linguoculturology.

Emotions are a specific way of reflecting the active process of human interaction with reality, as a result of which he has experiences that convey his individual attitude to certain realities of reality. Joy is a positive emotional state associated with social interactions, overcoming obstacles, achieving goals, and being able to satisfy needs

Phraseological units are an integral part of any language and are reflected in a person's life, the characteristics of his character, physical and emotional state. In conclusion, it can be concluded that most of the phraseological units expressing a state of joy in Russian and English are equivalent and have similar features in the components that make up the internal form of phraseological units, in full or partial coincidence of the image, in the presence of common standards and stereotypes, which indicates the universality of human thinking.

Phraseomatic meaning, according to A.V. Kunin, is invariant of information expressed by means of discrete language units, having non-transferred but complicated meanings.

There are some phraseologism about happiness and their definitions with examples:

over the moon

To be over the moon about something is to be very happy about something: so happy and excited that you imagine you could jump or fly over the moon!

We feel over the moon about the birth of our grandson.

on cloud nine

If you are on cloud nine you are extremely happy.

News headline: Nintendo 3DS users on Cloud 9 after free Wi-Fi deal announced.

in seventh heaven

To be in seventh heaven is also to be extremely happy, or in a state of bliss. In Islamic and Jewish faith there are seven heavens: the seventh is the dwelling place of God and the angels.

Take That fans were in seventh heaven when Robbie Williams agreed to rejoin the band on top of the world

If you are on top of the world you are enjoying great happiness, health or success.

My job is going well and I have a wonderful family: I feel on top of the world!

Good knowledge of the language is impossible without knowledge of its phraseology. Reasonable use of phraseological units makes speech more idiomatic. Unfortunately, there are few works in the English and American linguistic literature specifically devoted to the theory of phraseology, but even the most significant works available.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Kunin A.V. Course of phraseology of modern English. -M "High school", 1996, 380h.
2. Фразеологический словарь русского языка/ сост. Степанова М.И «ООО Виктория плюс» 2012г
3. <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/197412638.pdf>
4. <https://applied-research.ru/ru/article/view?id=7212>